

IMPLEMENTATION OF IOT BASED SMART ASSISTANCE GLOVES FOR SPEAKING IMPAIRED PEOPLE

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Abstract:

Communication between individual's vocal and hearing impairments and those without such impairments can be challenging. The sign language commonly used by individuals with these impairments is not easily understood by the general population, resulting in a communication barrier. Additionally, individuals who are paralyzed often require regular assistance. To address these challenges, we have developed a solution called the Implementation of IOT-based Smart assistance gloves for disabled individuals. Our gloves are designed to be simple yet highly effective compared to existing systems. The proposed system utilizes Arduino Uno and Raspberry Pi, with a wireless serial port module facilitating secure data transmission between the two modules. In emergencies, an alert message can be sent through the GSM module.

Key Words: Gloves, IOT, Flex Sensors, GSM.

1. Introduction:

A recent survey conducted in India revealed that there are millions of individuals with speech and hearing impairments, totaling up to 2.4 million people. These individuals face challenges in communicating with others on a daily basis and struggle to express their emotions. While people with disabilities often use sign language to communicate, this form of communication can be difficult for those without disabilities to understand. Additionally, learning sign language can be challenging for both individuals with disabilities and those without. This difficulty in communication can lead to social isolation and hinder the ability to voice opinions, a situation that is also true for individuals with paralysis who may struggle to move or communicate. To address these challenges, we have developed a specialized glove that enables individuals with disabilities to communicate their needs independently. While there are various existing approaches to this issue, our disabled assistance glove offers a faster and more efficient solution. Gesture recognition can be achieved through two methods: data glove-based and vision-based. Vision-based recognition, while effective, can be prone to inaccuracies due to noise interference and data processing challenges. On the other hand, data glove-based recognition is known for its faster response times. We have chosen a data glove-based approach for its accuracy, feasibility, and portability. Flex sensors within the glove detect finger movements and translate them into varying levels of resistance, allowing for a wide range of commands to be inputted. To enhance storage capacity and response speed, we have integrated an Arduino Uno board. The Raspberry Pi 3B, equipped with built-in Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and USB boot capabilities, connects to an Android app for seamless communication. Wireless serial port modules facilitate signal transmission between the Arduino Uno and Raspberry Pi, ensuring efficient data exchange.

Figure 1: IOT Data Processing System

2. Methodology:

Since there hasn't been much progress in aiding the crippled, we've developed a novel solution in the form of smart assistance gloves. The flex sensors in these gloves are programmed using an Arduino Uno board. By gathering finger motions, the flex sensor enables the gloves to produce equal outputs. After that, an Android app presents these outputs as phrases and speaks them loudly. The entire procedure is made possible by the

The APR33A3 board features 8 channels for voice recording and audio playback, utilizing the powerful APR33A series IC. This IC includes high-performance audio ADCs and DACs, providing a fully integrated solution with exceptional performance and integration of analog input, digital processing, and analog output functions. Specifically designed for simple key triggers, the APR33A series allows users to record and play messages with 1, 2, 4, or 8 voice messages by using a switch. The sample rate can be adjusted by varying resistor values. This board is ideal for applications requiring a simple interface or the need to limit the length of a single message, such as toys, message systems, answering machines, and more.

Figure 4: Flex Sensor

Bending-sensitive devices, or flex sensors, are widely used in many different fields, including wearable technology, robotics, and human-machine interfaces. The conductive substance applied to a flexible substrate serves as the building block for these sensors. The resistance of the conductive substance changes as the sensor is bent, depending on how much it is bent.

4. Block Diagram:

Figure 4: Block Diagram

Embedded Systems:

Figure 5: Embedded System

5. Working:

Smart gloves are used by the deaf and dumb to communicate their fundamental needs. The finger movement is detected by the flex sensor, which translates it into the appropriate commands. The Arduino Uno, which is attached to wireless serial port and GSM modules, stores these commands. There are two wireless

serial port modules used, one linked to the Raspberry Pi and the other to the Arduino. The Lora transceiver is used to send the recorded orders to the Raspberry Pi, allowing them to be broadcast as audio and shown on a webpage. The output is additionally shown on a mobile app, which enables the caregiver or assistant to be alerted right away in the event that the person moves. This notification can be sent to the caregiver even if they are not in close proximity to the person with impairment. The disabled person can utilize a unique, simple movement to alert their emergency contact and caregiver via email in the case of an emergency. This method provides an easy technique to monitor the well-being of the disabled person. Furthermore, the disabled person can talk and overcome any hearing or speech problems thanks to these gloves.

6. Frequency Response Analysis:

Smart gloves are used by the deaf and dumb to communicate their fundamental needs. The finger movement is detected by the flex sensor, which translates it into the appropriate commands. The Arduino Uno, which is attached to wireless serial port and GSM modules, stores these commands. There are two wireless serial port modules used, one linked to the Raspberry Pi and the other to the Arduino. The Lora transceiver is used to send the recorded orders to the Raspberry Pi, allowing them to be broadcast as audio and shown on a webpage. The output is additionally shown on a mobile app, which enables the caregiver or assistant to be alerted right away in the event that the person moves. This notification can be sent to the caregiver even if they are not in close proximity to the person with impairment. The disabled person can utilize a unique, simple movement to alert their emergency contact and caregiver via email in the case of an emergency. This method provides an easy technique to monitor the well-being of the disabled person. Furthermore, the disabled person can talk and overcome any hearing or speech problems thanks to these gloves.

7. Why Did We Select ESP 32:

The ESP32 is a well-liked choice for smart glove applications because to its features and adaptability. It enables functions including wireless communication, gesture recognition, temperature and accelerometer data collection, and haptic feedback when integrated into smart gloves. The dual Wi-Fi and Bluetooth capabilities, low cost, and power efficiency of the ESP32 WROOM allow the gloves to easily communicate with other devices or the internet. It is the ideal microcontroller module for enhancing the functionality of smart gloves, whether they are used for virtual reality, remote control, or health monitoring applications because of its processing capabilities and networking possibilities.

8. Implementing Flex Sensor and IoT:

One innovative method of tackling communication challenges is the integration of Internet of Things and flex sensors into a smart glove designed for those with speech issues. The glove's built-in flex sensors pick up on little finger motions and translate them into useful signals. Through Internet of Things connectivity, these signals are wirelessly transmitted to a connected device or a central processing unit. This enables real-time gesture interpretation, enabling effective nonverbal communication. The Internet of Things component also makes remote monitoring and customization possible, which enhances usability and accessibility. These technologies are used by the smart glove to help persons with speech impairments interact more freely with their surroundings and communicate effectively. This invention represents a significant advancement in inclusivity and empowerment for people who experience speech challenges in communication.

9. Hardware Setup:

Figure 6: Hardware

10. Result and Discussion:

As a result, the program gets the output and displays the relevant instructions on the homepage as well as within the application. Moreover, the speaker is used as the audio output when the output is supplied in audio format. A notification message is sent to the selected emergency contact in the case of an emergency.

Figure 7: Output

11. Conclusions:

As a result, the suggested model has the advantage of helping people who are paralyzed, deaf, or silent by giving the output commands via an android application and providing vocal output through a speaker. Data communication is rapid and secure when wireless serial port modules are used. GSM will send alert messages to the specified person in case of an emergency. This data-based gloves method reduces noise disturbances and streamlines the algorithms when compared to vision-based solutions. We can add more commands to this suggested model later on to make it even better. Speech recognition can be added to the data-based system to further enhance it through the use of AI. With home automation, we may use different gestures to control a variety of basic operations, like turning on appliances.

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